

Critical Review of Mission and Ministry in the 21st Century

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1. Introduction

The paper is basically centered on the topic of mission and ministry in the 21st century drawn from a critical perspective. Here the researcher initially draws a clear understanding of the various terminologies associated with mission and ministry and then delves on to the practical reflections in the contemporary world.

1.1 Terminology

1.1.1 Mission

Mission is the first term that must be defined. In their book *What is the Mission of the Church?*, **Kevin DeYoung and Greg Gilbert** propose that mission concerns, “being sent and being given a task.”¹ They argue that what Jesus sent his followers into the world to accomplish must remain the mission and priority of the church.² They further aver that Jesus’ mission mandate to the church remains entrenched in gospel proclamation and disciple-making.³

Samuel Escobar describes a different perspective of mission. Escobar provides an interesting analysis of the concept of mission, not because he defines mission so clearly, but because of his holistic understanding of mission. He joined Stott on the Lausanne Covenant drafting

¹Kevin DeYoung and Gregory D. Gilbert, *What is the Mission of the Church? Making Sense of Social Justice, Shalom, and Social Justice*, Kindle ed. (Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2011), 19.

² Ibid., 29.

³ Ibid., 53-54.

committee as a voice for the social implications of the church's mission.⁴ In his book *Christian Mission and Social Justice*, Escobar offers a corrective to what he argued was the popular view of missions as primarily a numerical and geographical expansion.⁵ He believes the mission of the church includes the uniqueness of the biblical gospel, but argues that churches should adopt a kingdom mindset where congregations in particular contexts can bring a practical ethos toward social change.⁶ For Escobar, the mission of the church includes pursuing justice.⁷ Escobar interprets mission in light of not only gospel proclamation, but also sacrificial service and pursuit of justice.

Christopher J. H. Wright argues for seeing the mission of God as holistic, including such biblical expectations as preaching the gospel, ministering to the needy and poor, pursuing justice, and offering education.⁸ Wright suggests that the church's mission must be holistic in scope which for him includes mandates for social action as well as evangelism.

John Stott himself suggested that mission carried with it two predominant but extreme positions. He presented the first extreme view of mission as verbal proclamation alone which is essentially evangelism in a foreign context.⁹ He argued that the second extreme was generally more ecumenical and declared that mission is bringing shalom or God's peace in social situations to the world.¹⁰ He primarily noted John's version of the commission in John 20:21 where Jesus said, "As the Father has sent me, even so I send you."¹¹ Stott affirmed the

⁴ John R. W. Stott, *The Lausanne Covenant* (Peabody, MA: Hendrickson Publishers, 2012), 9.

⁵ Samuel Escobar and John Driver, *Christian Mission and Social Justice* (Scottsdale, PA: Herald, 1978), 16.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 78.

⁷ *Ibid.*, 83.

⁸ Christopher J. H. Wright, *The Mission of God: Unlocking the Bible's Grand Narrative* (Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity, 2006), 23.

⁹ Stott, *Christian Mission in the Modern World*, 25-26.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 28-29.

¹¹ Stott believed neither of these positions clearly depicted the biblical expectations. He synthesized the extremes by using the Great Commission and the sending dynamic found in Scripture – God sending the Son and the Son sending the disciples. *Ibid.*, 37-40.

Great Commission's inclusion of proclamation, teaching, discipleship, and service by pointing out Jesus' mission was one of service which should be understood to be the mission of the church.

On one hand, Mohler, DeYoung, Gilbert, and Litfin emphasize the Commission mandate for redemption as the specific mission of the church. On the other hand, Escobar, Wright, and Stott contribute an important perspective to the church. They note that the Christian life and witness is necessarily broader than mere proclamation.

1.1.2 Evangelism

Evangelism was clearly and specifically defined in the **Lausanne Covenant**, which will provide the basic definition for this dissertation. Evangelism is most simply the spread of the good news concerning the death and resurrection of Jesus Christ.¹²

The paragraph on evangelism from the Lausanne Covenant explains,

To evangelize is to spread the good news that Jesus Christ died for our sins and was raised from the dead according to the Scriptures, and that as the reigning Lord he now offers the forgiveness of sins and the liberating gift of the Spirit to all who repent and believe. Our Christian presence in the world is indispensable to evangelism, and so is that kind of dialogue whose purpose is to listen sensitively to understand. But evangelism itself is the proclamation of the historical, biblical Christ as Savior and Lord, with a view to persuading people to come to him personally and so be reconciled to God.¹³

Stott and the Lausanne committee kept evangelism biblically specific. Evangelism should be understood as a part of the church's mission.

¹² John R. W. Stott, *The Lausanne Covenant: An Exposition and Commentary* (Minneapolis: World Wide, 1975), 20-21.

¹³ *Ibid.*, 20.

1.1.3 Social Responsibility

Stott and the Lausanne committee grounded social responsibility in God who created mankind in his image and pursues justice in the world today, as well ultimately in the final judgment.¹⁴ Furthermore, the committee was careful to delineate between evangelism and social responsibility, while they claim that both are “part of our Christian duty.”¹⁵ Social service is “Relieving human need, philanthropic activity, seeking to minister to individuals and families, works of mercy,”¹⁶ while social action is, “removing the causes of human need, political and economic activity, seeking to transform the structures of society, the quest for justice.”¹⁷ Stott argued that social service and social action should not be divorced from one another because some issues require political engagement and cannot be justly addressed apart from socio-political action.¹⁸

Thus, Stott and the Lausanne committee intrinsically connected areas of social ministry with socio-political action. In their mind, social responsibility contained more than ministering to immediate needs. It also anticipated and expected Christians to engage political issues ranging from the economy to injustice.

1.1.4 Social Justice

A variety of Christian thinkers have assumed social justice terminology. Samuel Escobar believed that the gospel itself contains the framework for helping individuals who face injustice as well as “challenging and sometimes transforming the evil structural roots of social injustice.”¹⁹ Escobar connected injustice to issues driven by economic situations like poverty

¹⁴ Stott, *The Lausanne Covenant: An Exposition and Commentary*, 25.

¹⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁷ Stott, *Issues Facing Christians Today*, 35.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*, 36.

¹⁹ Escobar, *The New Global Mission*, 148.

and oppression.²⁰ Within a theologically conservative framework, **Timothy Keller** stated, “God loves and defends those with the least economic and social power, and so should we. That is what it means to ‘do justice.’”²¹ **Brian McLaren** simply stated that justice was “the right use of power in our relationship with others.”²² These thinkers believe that social justice is learning to act publicly or socially in the just manner that God desires of his people.

1.2 Ministry in the 21st Century

The widely appreciated ecumenical document **Baptism, Eucharist and Ministry** (BEM) begins the Ministry part with a section on “The calling of the whole people of God.”²³ It points out the church lives through the liberating and renewing power of the Holy Spirit and is called to proclaim and prefigure the kingdom of God. Then it says: The Holy Spirit bestows on the community diverse and complementary gifts. These are for the common good of the whole people and are manifested in acts of service within the community and to the world. They may be gifts of communicating the Gospel in word and deed, gifts of healing, gifts of praying, gifts of teaching and learning, gifts of serving, gifts of guiding and following, gifts of inspiration and vision.²⁴ All members are called to discover, with the help of the community, the gifts they have received and to use them for the building up of the Church and for the service of the world to which the Church is sent.

²⁰ Ibid.

²¹ Timothy Keller, *Generous Justice - How God's Grace Makes Us Just*, (London: Hodder & Stoughton, 2010), 5.

²² Brian McLaren, “What is Justice?” in *The Justice Project*, ed. Brian McLaren, Elisa Padilla, and Ashley Bunting Seeber (Grand Rapids: Baker, 2009), 22.

²³ https://archive.org/stream/wccfops2.119/wccfops2.119_djvu.txt

²⁴ Ibid.,

1.3 Jesus Way of ministry

Ministry is essentially about the continuing ministry and mission of Jesus Christ. The risen Jesus promised the Spirit to empower the disciples to do so (John 20:21-22, Acts 1:8). Jesus' earthly ministry involved proclaiming, healing, exorcism, teaching, prophetic critique and symbolic action. The church is to be about preaching and teaching, healing and liberating, caring for people in particular the least and lost, challenging the powers in the world and at times performing symbolic actions. It is ministry of the whole people of God for the church is the body of Christ, his contemporary mouth, hands and feet (I Corinthians 12: 12-27). Jesus' ministry had a challenging, disturbing aspect, namely a prophetic dimension. The contemporary church needs to have this also.

Ministry in the way Jesus did ministry involved an apprenticeship style in which the disciples shared experiences with Jesus and were instructed by him to serve in the same manner he did (Mark 6:7-13, Luke 10:1-20). People are called into partnership with Jesus and others. Ministry involves both being Christ for others and meeting Christ in others (Matthew 25: 31-46).

Ministry is declaring the relationship God makes possible. It involves showing God's love and letting people know God loves them as a reflection of Jesus' compassion. We are to use our gifts and skills in the service of God. There are different types of ministries. There is a life giving, catalyst nature to ministry. The Spirit who empowers and enables ministry is the Spirit of life.

All are called but not all respond. The primary call is to discipleship. All who name Christ, including children, are to engage in some form of ministry. Baptism signifies belonging to

Jesus Christ and includes the expectation that people will join him in mission. Then there is a call to a vocation, some to ordained leadership. The call to leadership involves both the ordained and the non-ordained. The ordained have a particular lifelong calling to serve in leadership and are acknowledged by the church. Spiritual leadership as exercised by the ordained includes being a focus for the community and also encouraging and equipping others in their discipleship.

In a nut shell, Ministry includes: proclaiming the gospel, drawing inspiration; worship, focusing on God, prayer and discernment; pastoral care and counseling; teaching the faith, equipping and empowering people for ministry and mission; leadership in relation to small groups, fostering spiritual growth; being able to share faith, speaking God's word to situations; and serving the world, relating to the changing cultural context; advocacy and solidarity; peacekeeping and reconciliation.

1.4 Reflections

The following points are reflected based on the two weeks of consultation held at Wheaton College where participants from 30 nations, representing different churches and Christian mission agencies prayed about and then reflected upon the church's task in response to human need.²⁵

²⁵ "Transformation: The Church in Response to Human Need" (12 June 1983)

<https://www.lausanne.org/content/statement/transformation-the-church-in-response-to-human-need>

Note: text from *The Church in Response to Human Need*, edited by Vinay Samuel and Christopher Sugden (Grand Rapids, USA and Oxford, UK: Wm. B. Eerdmans Publ. Co. and Regnum Books, 1987), p. xi.

1.4.1. Christian Social Involvement

Christians stemming from the lower, backward section of the society face the grim of the reality of increasing poverty and misery, rampant oppression and exploitation by their masters do feel they are denied the basic biblical injunctions such as to defend the cause of the weak, maintain the rights of the poor and oppressed (Ps. 82:3), and practice justice and love (Mic. 6:8).²⁶ Rowan Williams believes that many Christian doctrines also reveal social involvement as the indispensable task of the church. He argues that the meanings of sacraments, especially Baptism and Eucharist, should challenge “how there might be a social order in which the disadvantaged and even the criminal could trust that the common resource of a society would work for their good.”²⁷

1.4.2 Not only Development but Transformation

Development is often described as a process in which nations and people become part of the existing international economic order. The immense need is for replacing the word ‘development’ with “transformation. Transformation encourages individuals who freely pursue their own self-interests needs to be challenged on the basic of the biblical teaching on stewardship (Luke 12:13-21; 16:13-15; Phil. 2:1-4). The goal of transformation is best described by the biblical vision of the Kingdom of God that is striving to bring peace among individuals, races, and nations by overcoming prejudices, fears, and preconceived ideas about others. It means sharing basic recourses like food, water, the means of healing, and knowledge.”²⁸

²⁶ Duncan B. Forrester, *On Human Worth*, (London: SCM Press, 2001), 115.

²⁷ Rowan Williams, *On Christian Theology* (UK: Blackwell, 2000), 220.

²⁸ “Transformation: The Church in Response to Human Need” (12 June 1983)

<https://www.lausanne.org/content/statement/transformation-the-church-in-response-to-human-need>

1.4.3 The Stewardship of Creation

All human beings are God's creatures. Human beings have been slow to recognize that we do not own the earth but we manage and enhance it in anticipation of Christ's return. We are responsible for taking care of the world we live in and for sharing all the wonders and resources the earth gives us. Our changing environment prompts us to stop and think about how we live on our planet. We are called to respond and to adopt new ways of living as Pope Francis highlights in his encyclical, *Laudato Si': On the Care of our Common Home*.²⁹ It is the world's poorest communities who are affected by changes to our planet. The earth is God's gift to all generations. The meaning of stewardship is that the poor have equal rights to God's resources (Deut. 15:8-9).

1.4.4 Social Justice and Mercy

The understanding that poverty is not a necessary evil but often the result of social, economic, political, and religious systems marked by injustice, exploitation, and oppression. The mission of the church includes both the proclamations of the Gospel and its demonstration. We must therefore evangelize, respond to immediate human needs, and press for social transformation. Our ministry of justice and healing is not limited to fellow Christians but also should extend to the stranger (Matt. 5:43-48).³⁰ Our involvement with strangers is not only through charity, but also through economic policies toward the poor. Our economic and political action is inseparable from evangelism.

²⁹ Stewardship of Creation,

<http://www.caritas.org.au/learn/catholic-social-teaching/stewardship-of-creation>

³⁰ Brandon Vogt, *With Saints and Social Justice: A Guide to Changing the World*

<http://www.patheos.com/blogs/the anchoress/2014/07/01/social-justice-and-mercy-two-threads-of-the-same-helix/>

1.4.5. The Local Church and Transformation

The local church is the basic unit of Christian society. The recognition that across the generations local churches have been the vehicle for the transmission of the Gospel of Jesus Christ, and that their primary, though not their only, role is a threefold ministry: the worship and praise of God, the proclamation in word and deed of the Gospel of the grace of God, and the nurture, instruction, and discipleship of those who have received Jesus Christ into their lives.

Widows, prisoners, the poor, and the strangers are people who are particularly the responsibility of the local church (Gal. 6:10). We should seek to minister to the poor in our local areas who are not members of the church (James 1:27; Rom. 12:17). Christians should carefully consider the issues and manner in which they protest so that the identity and message of the church is neither blurred nor drowned.³¹

1.4.6. Christians Aid Agencies and Transformation

Churches around the world have throughout history displayed active concern for the needs around them and countries to serve the needy. In all of our programs and actions we should remember that God in His sovereignty and love is already active in the communities we seek to serve (Acts 14:17; 17:23; Rom. 2:9-15). Agencies, therefore, should give adequate priority to listening sensitively to the concerns of these communities, facilitating a two-way process in communication and local ownership of programs.³²

³¹ Bob Moffit, *If Jesus Were Mayor: How Your Local Church Can Transform Your Community* (Grand Rapids, MI:Kregel Publications, 2007), 45.

³² "Transformation: The Church in Response to Human Need" (12 June 1983)
<https://www.lausanne.org/content/statement/transformation-the-church-in-response-to-human-need>

1.4.7. Peace and Reconciliation

As a prophetic sign, the churches are called to speak out against injustice and to advocate peace. In the denunciation of injustice, in the solidarity with those who are oppressed, and in the accompaniment of victims, the churches participate in the *missio Dei* of mending the world and bringing it toward the “new creation” of the reconciled (cf. 2 Cor 5:17).³³

Social reconciliation focuses upon healing the memories or building a common future together. Whenever reconciliation is achieved, the experience of it as a gift of free grace from God can be the most moving and effective way of speaking about God’s design for the world, of how the world is being drawn back into God, its Creator.³⁴

1.4.8. Advocacy and Solidarity

Advocacy is the act of supporting a cause or proposal and requires an understanding of the problem or issue, solid analysis of the political environment and a coherent proposal for its solution. Advocacy encompasses the education and mobilization of citizens, so they can become involved in developing and promoting policies they care about.³⁵ In the words of **Rev. Dr Olav Fykse Tveit**, “The Church is not exempted from upholding the value, dignity and rights of every human being who is created in the image of God. It can never be outside the calling of the Church to try to protect and remind states of their responsibility to protect every

³³ Initial Statement Towards an Ecumenical Declaration on Just Peace, “The Nature and Mission of the Church,” para 52.

http://www.overcomingviolence.org/fileadmin/dov/files/iepc/peace_declarations/drafting_group/Initial_Statement_JustPeaceDeclaration_p11-17.pdf

³⁴ Initial Statement Towards an Ecumenical Declaration on Just Peace, “The Nature and Mission of the Church,” para 72.

http://www.overcomingviolence.org/fileadmin/dov/files/iepc/peace_declarations/drafting_group/Initial_Statement_JustPeaceDeclaration_p11-17.pdf

³⁵ http://www.confrontglobalpoverty.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/CCGP_what_is_advocacy_US16107.pdf

human being! We shall never ask the question of Cain (Gen 4:9): Am I my brother's keeper?"³⁶

1.5 Conclusion

The centrality of one's understanding of mission differs from person to person depending on the perspective he/she embarks upon. Typically drawing from the missionary movements, the initial thrust was centered largely on evangelism, then later down the attention of transformation of the communities were stressed. Christian Mission has always been the same right from the start. We understand that it is God's mission first. We are here because God has moved towards us, into our midst, and drawn us into his own movement of love, drawn us back to him through Christ praying in him by the power of the Spirit. That's God's mission and all that we ever do is to reflect its movement, and be carried along in the slipstream of God's movement into the world, gathering the world back to him.

God's has given us the responsibility of witnessing to his own journey into the depths of the world and back to heaven, of telling that story and making that life available. But perhaps the simplest and most central thing in all this, is the expression which Jesus uses in Matthew 10.8, where the rationale for all we do in mission and in every other area of our discipleship, 'Freely you have received; freely give'.³⁷

³⁶ Olav Fykse Tveit, "To Be One Voice of Advocacy for Peace and Justice," (04 October 2010), Meeting of the Commission of the Churches on International Affairs (CCIA), Saint Vlash Theological Academy - Durrës, Albania.
<https://www.oikoumene.org/en/resources/documents/general-secretary/speeches/to-be-one-voice-of-advocacy-for-peace-and-justice>

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